

The Effect of Audit Quality on Corporate Governance Mechanism and Financial Reporting

By

Samuel Akpovwri Eyenubo¹, Stephen Akpo Ejubekpokpo²

Department of Economics, Delta State University, Abraka Nigeria.

ejirosteve2@yahoo.com; steveuum@gmail.com +2347065888235

eyenuboakpovwre@gmail.com, +2348036653297

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the impact of audit quality on corporate governance mechanism and financial reporting quality in Nigeria. Descriptive and panel data analysis are utilized. The results of the descriptive statistics show that financial reporting quality is low in Nigeria compared to developed economies. The panel regressions reveal that ownership structure, block holders and director shareholder in the company positively influence financial reporting quality. In conclusion, the study revealed that audit quality affected the viability of corporate governance audit committee variables in improving the FRQ of firms in Nigeria.

Keywords: *audit quality, corporate governance, descriptive analysis, financial reporting, Nigeria, paneldata analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Financial reporting quality has become crucial in the 21st century owing to the recurring global scandals and challenges which constitute adverse effect on the productivity and financial statements of firms. Financial reporting quality (FRQ) of firms can be enhanced through good corporate governance mechanism (Norwani et al., 2011). High FRQ could improve investor confidence and likewise improve investment efficiency of the economy. However, the developing country Nigeria has been greatly plagued by the crisis of accounting and auditing scandals, corporate failures, and ethical negligence of the auditors. To handle these crises, Nigeria has taken good steps towards enhancing their corporate governance (Adeyemi, 2006; Ofoegbu & Okoye, 2006; Salaudeen, Ibikunle & Chima, 2015; Oluwagbemiga, 2014) to improve the transparency and enforcement of laws and corporate governance best code (FRCN, 2015). The weak corporate governance practice evident in the country has led to poor financial reporting quality, while the ineffective and efficient of the auditor and the complacent attitude of the board of directors were responsible for escalating the crisis.

Previous studies on corporate governance have explored its importance to firms' FRQ. Most of the studies (Kantudu & Samila, 2015, Nyor, 2013, Eknieh, 2009, Nwonyuku, 2012) focused on the direct impact of corporate governance of FRQ and found mixed and inconsistent findings. However, studies have not really

considered the influence of audit quality such as big4 and audit tenure on FRQ variables. Similarly, corporate governance variables on the relationship between audit quality and FRQ have received less attention (Adeyemi, Okpala & Dabor, 2012; Hassan & Bello, 2013). From Baron and Kenny (1986) and Hays (2009), the inconsistent finding from previous studies suggested the introduction of big 4 and audit tenure as a moderating variable. In spite of all the challenges, few studies have focused on assessing the interaction of big 4 and audit tenure with FRQ and this is the gap this paper want to fill. The link between corporate governance and FRQ is the subject of only a few studies, which implies that studies that investigate the link between FRQ audit tenure and big 4 are scarce are still in infant stage. Categorically, for the reason of this paper, financial reporting quality is defined as the financial statements that will reveal the financial position in the annual report and build up the investors' confidence and make the reliable decision about providing wealth in a firm (Eyenubo et al., 2017). There is a need for empirical studies that investigate the collective impact of block holder, director shareholder, board size, board independence, committee independence, committee diligence, committee size, and committee expertise. This is what this paper is set to examine.

Empirical Reviews

The financial reporting quality is the dependent variable of the study and it encompasses other variables in the study. FRQ is an important requirement for attracting investment as investors make decisions and allocate their resources based on financial report. The financial reporting quality is an indication that the firm financial statement is free from fraud and the extent of the audit work performed is clearly communicated to the investors and the general public to give a true and fair view of the financial statement (Agrawal & Chadha, 2005). FRQ is a very vital component of the company's transaction that would enable the shareholder and the public aware of their investment efficiency in an organization (Deloitte, 2011). Ekineh (2009) posits that financial reporting quality is a key barometer of the state of health of an organization and should be reliable, accurate and timely to meet the desire of the shareholder and investors.

Audit quality is very important, as it affects the credibility, reliability of the financial statement and protects the interest of the shareholder. It could also improve the rate of compliance and transparency of financial statement via higher voluntary disclosure in the annual report (Barros, Boubaker & Hamrouni, 2013) and reduces earnings management manipulations (Sergio Almeida-Santos, 2013). Higher audit quality militates against agency problem that results in the separation of ownership and control (Al Ajmi, 2009), and hence being very important in solving the opportunistic behavior of the agent and the principal interest (Chen, Elder & Hiseh, 2007). Audit quality provides a monitoring and controlling role of the firms independently (Francis & Wang, 2008).

Previous studies use different proxies for audit quality such as audit engagement tenure (Al-Ajmi, 2009), size of audit firm (DeFond & Lennox, 2011), audit fees (Haat et al. 2008), audit structure (Kaplan, Menon & Williams, 1990), and audit rotation (Eragabe et al. 2012). Consequently, prior researcher advocated a significant relationship of audit quality with better monitoring competence with the size of audit firm (DeAngelo, 1981). Barbu et al., 2014 asserted that larger firms could disclose more information and have more resources and expertise to shareholders than smaller firms, while Peecher and Piercey (2008) asserted that lower audit quality could have an adverse effect with litigation on the part of the auditor. These corporate scandals had their roots in auditor's failures. Therefore, arising from the inconsistent and mixed findings between these schools of thought, the study reexamines the moderating relationship between big 4, audit tenure and FRQ using the following hypotheses (H2a-H2h).

Bhattachryya (2012) opines that corporate governance is strongly associated with corporate FRQ. It is difficult to isolate FRQ from corporate governance because the product of FRQ depends on the strength of the corporate governance. Good corporate governance therefore initiates a system that could put in place process that can facilitate FRQ. The effective and efficient corporate governance cannot be realized by company regulation policy only, but also depending on the internal factors that could assist the self-

mechanism of the system. Abbott et al. (2016) asserted that companies with stronger internal corporate governance structure and practice produce better FRQ with corporate governance variables from past studies. Consequently, when there are mixed and inconsistent findings between the outcome and the predictive variables the study reexamines the relationship between the corporate governance audit committee and FRQ.

Prior literature examined the link between block holder and financial reporting quality and documented that the result remains mixed in the extant literature. Nodehi, Largani and Nokashti (2015) investigate the effect of block holder on financial reporting quality and the findings reveal that block holder have a relationship with financial reporting quality. Dou et al. (2013) reported that block holder is positively significantly relationship with financial reporting quality as related incomes determination and price response to income. Likewise, the core responsibility of the director is the overseeing, controlling and monitoring of manager and the workforce to ensure that the internal and external system of the organization is working well. Jensen and Meckling (1976) assert that the way to align director interest with the shareholders that will reduce the gap thereby taking delight in doing adequate overseeing and monitoring activities that could improve financial reporting quality.

The board size is one of the notable governance characteristics utilized by management in ensuring the business activities are properly conducted (Said et al., 2009). Previous studies have discussed the relationship of the size of board director in relation with corporate governance and financial reporting quality disclosures (Abidin et al., 2009; Haji, 2013) and the result are mixed from previous literature. Literature suggested the result for board size depend on the size of the board whether small or large and their independence.

Fama and Jensen (1983) posit that board independence has the duty to evaluate the quality, integrity and credibility of financial statement and ensure top managers are accountable, transparent and diligent with the financial statements. Additionally, board independence is expected to be independent to reduce the agency conflict problem and could enhance a high financial reporting process. The capability of independence of the board is to monitor firm's manager composition and mechanism for internal control with enough level of external scrutiny that will play an important oversight role in the financial reports.

Robinson and Owens-Jackson (2009) asserted that independence is most persuasive theoretically and empirically because it is regarded as one of the vital variables that have a relationship with audit committee effectiveness. Independent director is one who has no significant transaction with the firm, not of the current employee of the firm, professional advisor to the firm former officer or employee of the firm or related entity, a relative of management, officer of significant suppliers or customers of the firm, and interlocking director.

Robinson and Owen-Jackson (2009) posit that audit committee diligence refers to the enthusiasm of audit committee members to follow their terms of reference and goals. The meetings of the audit committee enhance the corporate goals and promote the efficiency of the committee. Diligent audit committee meeting often has a positive association with high financial reporting quality.

The audit committee size is said to be the most researchable features of economic disclosure and recognized this component as positively associated with higher disclosure of financial statements (Barako et al., 2007). Consequently, the size of the committee depends on the size of the company and other relevant factors related to the firm.

The importance of having an expert in an organization remains very vital because a firm must have to deal with accounting fundamental that needs the job of an expert in the field. The study is to scrutinize the possible effect of having experts as members of the audit committee in enhancing its effectiveness which eventually leads to an enhanced financial reporting quality (Krishna et al., 2011). Deloitte (2011) suggested

that the committee should have members with both accounting and legal background considering the committee will also involve in the handling of matters involving financial reporting risks.

Audit quality is one of the vital components that can make financial reports relevant and reliable for investors and shareholders confidence. They do this by ensuring that the audit quality the internal and external auditors are efficient and effective in their audit engagement. Furthermore, the existence of an audit committee and audit quality could affect the quality of financial reporting quality (Agrawal & Chadha, 2005; Beasley et al., 2009).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the view of scope of this article which aims at investigating the impact of audit quality on corporate governance mechanism and financial reporting quality in Nigeria, the following hypotheses are formulated and stated in null form as follows. **H1a-H1h:** There is a significant relationship between the corporate governance, audit committee and financial reporting quality in Nigeria stock exchange. **H2a-H2h:** Audit quality significantly moderates the relationship between corporate governance and audit committee and financial reporting quality in Nigeria firms (big 4 H2a-H2h; audit tenure H2a1-H2h1).

Measurement of Variables

The dependent variable to be analyzed for this study is financial reporting quality (FRQ). These variables have been adopted as a measure of FRQ based on their extensive usage in the existing literature (Alrazi et al., 2009). FRQ is measured using disclosure index. The corporate governance variables adopted in this study are measured with various ways such as, Block holders is measured as the total shareholding by shareholders that own minimum shares of 5% in the company shares, Big 4 is determined by a dichotomous variable whereby a score of 1 is given in situations where the firm is audited by a big 4 audit firm and a score of 0 otherwise and so on.

Empirical Result

This study employed econometric analysis (a panel regression) over the period of 2011 to 2015. Data collected were winsorized at 1% to reduce the effect of the outlier (Dehnel, 2014). Furthermore, the Hausman specification test was conducted to make a choice between fixed effect (FE) and random effect (RE) models (Green, 2008). The results of the Hausman specification test were all significant, indicating p-values $\chi^2 = 59.77$ and 74.31 , for FRQ model for the direct relationship respectively. The result revealed FE to be an appropriate model for the study. The various models for the study are defined as follows.

Model 1:

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BLOCSHARE_{it} + \beta_2 DIRESHARE_{it} + \beta_3 BODSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BODIND_{it} + \beta_5 ACIND_{it} + \beta_6 ACDIL_{it} + \beta_7 ACSIZE_{it} + \beta_8 ACEXP_{it} + \beta_9 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_{10} PROF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Model 2:

$$\begin{aligned}
FRQ_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_2 PROF_{it} + \beta_3 BLOCSHARE_{it} + \beta_4 DIRESHARE_{it} \\
& + \beta_5 BODSIZE_{it} + \beta_6 BODIND_{it} + \beta_7 ACIND_{it} + \beta_8 ACDIL_{it} + \beta_9 ACSIZE_{it} \\
& + \beta_{10} ACEXP_{it} + \beta_{11} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{12} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{13} BLOCSHARE_{it} BIG4_{it} \\
& + \beta_{14} DIRESHARE_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{15} BODSIZE_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{16} BODIND_{it} BIG4_{it} \\
& + \beta_{17} ACIND_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{18} ADIL_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{19} ACSIZE_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{20} ACEXP_{it} BIG4_{it} \\
& + \beta_{21} BLOCSHARE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{22} DIRESHARE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} \\
& + \beta_{23} BODSIZE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{24} BODIND_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{25} ACIND_{it} AUDTEN_{it} \\
& + \beta_{26} ACDIL_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{27} ACSIZE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{28} ACEP_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where the corresponding subscripts denotes the panel data notation; i = the firm (cross-sectional unit), t = the time period, i.e., from 2011 to 2015, ε = the error term, while β is the regression slope coefficient. Models 1 and 2 test the hypotheses H1 and H2, with the following notations:

FRQ = FRQ, BLOCSHARE=Block shareholder, DIRESHARE=Directors' shareholding, BODSIZE=Board size, BODIND=Board independence, ACSIZE=Audit committee size, ACIND=Audit committee independence, ACEXP=Audit committee expertise, ACDIL=Audit committee diligence, BIG 4=Big 4, FSIZE=Firm size, PROF=Profitability, AUDTEN=Auditor Tenure, ε =Error term.

The Modified Wald test for GroupWise heteroskedasticity conducted suggests the presence of heteroskedasticity for all the models. This is because the chi-squares obtained for the models result shows that the chi-square $\chi^2=17.57$ and 11.13 , for Models 1 and 2 respectively, were all statistically significant at 1%. In addition, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data was conducted. The results of the test show that the f-values for models 1 and 2 were 276.858 and 299.804 , while their associated probabilities were not statistically significant (p-value > 0.10). To rectify the issues of heteroskedasticity, this study using robust standard error estimates based the commands "xtreg cluster code" (Hoechle, 2007).

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics reveals that the mean mandatory financial statement score was 0.68 (68%) with a minimum score of 0.22 (22%) and a maximum of 1.00 (100%). The result shows that on the average, the sampled companies had average financial reports which show high financial reporting quality as measured using the index. In describing the hypotheses of the variables that includes all companies at whole, block holders (BLOCSHARE) of the sampled companies held 20.14% of the shares while director shareholder (DIRESHARE) held the share of the sampled companies with a maximum 97% and a minimum of 0% and the average of 20% were in the hand of directors. This result shows that for the sampled companies, only a few percentages of the company's shares were in the possession of the board of directors. Furthermore, the mean for the total number of directors on the board (BSIZE) is 8.45, with a standard deviation of 2.11.

This study carefully examined the correlation coefficients of financial reporting quality and independent variables and found that no correlation coefficient between a pair of variables in this study exceeded the threshold of 0.90, which suggested as an indication of multicollinearity. Thus, the conclusion can be made that the choice of these variables would not result in misspecification. This was also confirmed by the variance inflation factor (VIF), which showed a value of 1.32. This value is less than the threshold value of 10, and therefore suggests no serious problem of multicollinearity.

Regression Analysis Results

In this section, the results of the relationship between corporate governance, audit committee and FRQ and the moderating effect of audit quality on the corporate governance audit committee and FRQ are presented.

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BLOCSHARE_{it} + \beta_2 DIRESHARE_{it} + \beta_3 BODSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BODIND_{it} + \beta_5 ACIND_{it} + \beta_6 ACDIL_{it} + \beta_7 ACSIZE_{it} + \beta_8 ACEXP_{it} + \beta_9 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_{10} PROF_{it} + \varepsilon_i \quad (3)$$

Table 1: Fixed Effects Regression Results for Financial Reporting Quality

Variables	H	Exp Sign	M1
			β (t stat)
Constant			-0.64 (-0.63)
BLOCKSHARE	H1a	+	0.01 (4.71) ***
DIRESHARE	H1b	+	3.27 (5.05) ***
BODSIZE	H1c	+	0.02 (1.32)
BODIND	H1d	+	-0.18 (-1.27)
ACIND	H1e	+	-0.23 (-0.75)
ACDIL	H1f	+	0.03 (2.01) **
ACSIZE	H1g	+	0.08 (5.32) ***
ACEXP	H1h	+	-5.66 (-7.17) ***
FSIZE			0.08 (1.24)
PROF			0.01 (0.99)

Notes: The coefficient values are presented with the t-statistics in the parenthesis, *p<.10; **p<.05; ***p<.01. Probabilities represent one-tailed when the direction of the coefficient is consistent with expectations, two-tailed otherwise.

H1c and H1e: The result suggests that the size of the board and the independence of the audit committee does not influence the quality of financial reporting. This result fails to provide support for the prediction in hypotheses that there exists a positive relationship between board size, audit committee independence and financial reporting quality. The plausible reasons could be that larger boards are likely to be less effective and likely to have a lower degree of independence and expertise than smaller boards. They are therefore likely to lack experts on specific issues such as financial reporting quality.

H1a, H1b, H1f, and H1g: The result shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between the variables (BLOCSHARE, DIRESHARE, ACDIL, ACSIZE) and financial reporting quality. The results, therefore, provides support for hypotheses. The positive results of this study support the principle of the agency and stakeholder theory that posits that block shareholders in firms will be highly visible in the public eye and more likely to disclose more information to improve their public relations and corporate image.

H1d and H1h: The results show that the relationship between board independence (BODIND), audit committee expertise (ACEXP) and financial reporting quality are negatively insignificant and significant respectively. Other things being equal, the result suggests that the independence of the board and expertise of the audit committee reduces the quality of financial reporting. The result, therefore, fails to provide support for H1d and H1h.

Moderating Effect of Big 4 and Audit Tenure on Corporate Governance Audit Committee and FRQ

Model 2 result shows that the R^2 for the fixed effects regression is 14%. The results show the variation in financial reporting quality that is explained by the moderating effect of audit quality in interaction with the corporate governance mechanism and audit committee characteristics. This is regressed against the dependent variable to determine the moderating impact. These models are presented in equations as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
FRQ_{it} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_2 PROF_{it} + \beta_3 BLOC SHARE_{it} + \beta_4 DIRESHARE_{it} \\
& + \beta_5 BODSIZE_{it} + \beta_6 BODIND_{it} + \beta_7 ACIND_{it} + \beta_8 ACDIL_{it} + \beta_9 ACSIZE_{it} \\
& + \beta_{10} ACEXP_{it} + \beta_{11} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{12} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{13} BLOC SHARE_{it} BIG4_{it} \\
& + \beta_{14} DIRESHARE_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{15} BODSIZE_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{16} BODIND_{it} BIG4_{it} \\
& + \beta_{17} ACIND_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{18} ADIL_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{19} ACSIZE_{it} BIG4_{it} + \beta_{20} ACEXP_{it} BIG4_{it} \\
& + \beta_{21} BLOC SHARE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{22} DIRESHARE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{23} BODSIZE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} \\
& + \beta_{24} BODIND_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{25} ACIND_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{26} ACDIL_{it} AUDTEN_{it} \\
& + \beta_{27} ACSIZE_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \beta_{28} ACEXP_{it} AUDTEN_{it} + \varepsilon_i
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Table 2: Fixed Effects Regression Results for Financial Reporting Quality

Variables	H	Exp Sign	M2
			β (t stat)
Constant			0.11(0.13)
BLOCKSHARE	H1a	+	0.01(4.56) ***
DIRESHARE	H1b	+	2.40(1.67) *
BODSIZE	H1c	+	0.02(1.47)
BODIND	H1d	+	-0.34(-2.46) **
ACIND	H1e	+	-0.26(-0.94)
ACDIL	H1f	+	0.02(1.54)
ACSIZE	H1g	+	0.06(0.92)
ACEXP	H1h	+	-7.27(-1.37)
BIG4	H2a	+	
AUDTENU	H2b	+	
FSIZE			0.05(1.70) *
PROF			0.00(0.21)
BLOCBIG4	H3a	?	-0.01(-1.33)
DIRBIG4	H3b	?	0.21(0.94)
BSIZEBIG4	H3c	?	-0.02(-0.66)
BINDBIG4	H3d	?	-0.39(-1.65) *
ACINDBIG4	H3e	?	-0.06(-0.16)
ADILBIG4	H3f	?	-0.06(-2.15) **
ACSIZEBIG4	H3g	?	0.01(0.05)
ACEXPBIG4	H3h	?	
BLOCTEN	H4a	?	0.01(1.08)
DIRTEN	H4b		-0.05(-0.24)
BSIZETEN	H4c		-0.00(-0.10)
BINDTEN	H4d		-0.42(-1.80)*
ACINDTEN	H4e		0.08(0.20)
ADILTEN	H4f		-0.00(-0.00)
ACSIZTEN	H4g		-0.06(-0.81)
ACEXPTEN	H4h		

Notes: The coefficient values are presented with the t-statistics in the parenthesis, *p<.10; **p<.05; ***p<.01. Probabilities represent one-tailed when the direction of the coefficient is consistent with

expectations, two-tailed otherwise. AUDTENU, BIG4, ACEXPBIG4 and ACEXPTEN are omitted because of collinearity.

H2d, H2f and H2d1: The result shows a significant relationship between the various moderating terms (BINDBIG4, ADILBIG4, BINDTEN) and financial reporting quality with respect to β s and P-values suggesting that big four auditors moderate the relationship between the variables.

H2a, H2b, H2c, H2e, H2g, H2a1, H2b, H2c1, H2e1, H2f1 and H2g1: The result shows an insignificant relationship between the moderating terms (BLOCBIG4, DIRBIG4, BSIZEBIG4, ACINDBIG4, ACSIZEBIG4, BLOCTEN, DIRETEN, BSIZETEN, ACINDTEN, ADILTEN, ACSIZETEN) and financial reporting quality with respect to β s and P-values, suggesting that big four auditors do not moderate the relationship between variables. The results do not support hypotheses that big four auditors moderate the relationship between the variables.

Thus, H2h1 and H2h: The result for the relationship between the moderating terms (ACEXPTEN, ACEXPBIG4) and financial reporting quality was omitted from the robust fixed effect regression due to the problem of collinearity as such the study was not able to accept or reject hypothesis 2h which states that auditor tenure and big four moderates the relationship between audit committee expertise and financial reporting quality.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of audit quality on the corporate governance audit committee and FRQ in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study, corporate governance audit committee mechanism influences FRQ, but the significance of this influence is contingent on the peculiar corporate governance mechanism circumstances driving the audit quality in the environment in which a firm operates. This is reflected in the mixed findings established in the results of Models 1 and 2. The study further revealed that audit quality affected the viability of corporate governance audit committee variables in improving the FRQ firms in Nigeria. These findings have important theoretical and managerial implications. Theoretically, this study advances the corporate governance audit committee literature by providing evidence on the importance of incorporating the impact of audit quality in formulating FRQ policies.

This study is useful in drawing up future corporate governance regulatory reforms and financial reporting quality matters of Nigeria's socio-economic environment. The regulatory authorities in Nigeria should give adequate attention to this issue to cope with the challenges of enforcing financial statement matters in future corporate governance reforms. The limitations of this current study and suggestion for future research are as follows. This study relied exclusively on a short panel data, and as such drawing strong causal inferences should be done with caution and this is the major limitation. Future researchers might consider expanding the data by adopting a longitudinal panel design. As an alternative of using the annual reports as the main unit of analysis, future studies may also adopt other means of information to determine the levels of the financial statement such as interim reports and corporate press releases.

REFERENCES

- Abidin, Z. Z., Kamal, N. M., & Jusoff, K. (2009). Board structure and corporate performance in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 150-164.
- Adeyemi, S. B., Okpala, O., & Dabor, E. L. (2012). Factors affecting audit quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(20)198-209.
- Agrawal, A., & Chadha, S. (2005). Corporate governance and accounting scandals. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 48(2), 371-406.

- Al-Ajmi, J. (2009). Audit firm, corporate governance, and audit quality: Evidence from Bahrain. *Advances in accounting*, 25(1), 64-74.
- Alrazi, B., Sulaiman, M., & Ahmad, N. N. N. (2009). A longitudinal examination of environmental reporting practices in Malaysia. *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 11(1), 37-72.
- Barako, D. G., & Tower, G. (2007). Corporate governance and bank performance: Does ownership matter? Evidence from Kenyan banking sector. *Corporate Ownership and Control*, 4(2), 133-144.
- Barbu, E. M., Dumontier, P., Feleagă, N., & Feleagă, L. (2014). Mandatory environmental disclosures by companies complying with IASs/IFRSs: The cases of France, Germany, and the UK. *The International Journal of Accounting*, 49(2), 231-247.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The moderator-mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173-1182.
- Barros, C. P., Boubaker, S., & Hamrouni, A. (2013). Corporate governance and voluntary disclosure in France. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 29(2), 561-578.
- Beasley, M. S., Carcello, J. V., Hermanson, D. R., & Neal, T. L. (2009). The audit committee oversight process. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 26(1), 65-122.
- Chen, K. Y., Elder, R. J., & Hsieh, Y. M. (2007). Corporate governance and earnings management: The implications of corporate governance best-practice principles for Taiwanese listed companies. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 3(2), 73-105.
- DeAngelo, L. E. (1981). Auditor independence, 'low balling', and disclosure regulation. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 3(2), 113-127.
- DeFond, M. L., & Lennox, C. S. (2011). The effect of SOX on small auditor exits and audit quality. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 52(1), 21-40.
- Dehnel, G. (2014). Winsorization Methods in Polish Business Survey. *Statistics in Transition—new series*, 15(1), 97-110.
- Dou, Y., Hope, O. K., Thomas, W. B., & Zou, Y. (2013). Blockholder heterogeneity and financial Reporting Quality. Working paper, New York University, University of Toronto, of Oklahoma, and George Washington University, 1-45.
- Ekineh, D. (2009). Reform agenda for corporate governance in Nigeria: Disclosure and reporting requirement. A paper presented at IOD's Corporate Governance Workshop in Lagos.
- Eyenubo, S. A., Mohamed, M., & Ali, M. (2017). An empirical analysis on the financial reporting quality of the quoted firms in Nigeria: Does audit committee size matter? *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(9), 50-63.
- Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria Act (2015). Act (6) 98: Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, Lagos.
- Francis, J. R., & Wang, D. (2008). The joint effect of investor protection and big 4 audits on earnings quality around the world. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 25(1), 157-191.
- Haji, A. A. (2013). The trend of CSR disclosures and the role of corporate governance attributes: The case of Shari'ah compliant companies in Malaysia. *Issues in Social and Environmental Accounting*, 6(3), 68-94.
- Hassan, S. U., & Bello, A. (2013). Firm characteristics and financial reporting quality of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting, Banking and Management*, 1(6), 47-63.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- Kantudu, A. S., & Samaila, I. A. (2015). Board characteristics, independent audit committee and financial reporting quality of oil marketing firms: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Finance, Accounting and Management*, 6(2), 34-40.
- Nodehi, A. T., Largani, M., & Nokashti, S. B. (2015). The effects of block holders on the quality of financial reporting in the listed companies in Tehran Stock Exchange Cumhuriyet. *University faculty of Science Journal*, 36(3), 3432-3439.

- Norwani, N. M., Mohammad, Z.Z., & Chek, I. T. (2011), Corporate governance failure audit impact on financial reporting within selected companies. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2 (21), 205-214.
- Nwonyuku, K. N. (2012). Corporate governance regulation: The key factor to credible financial reporting in Nigeria, 1-46. Available at SSRN 2600221.
- Ofoegbu, G. & Okoye, E. (2006). The relevance of accounting of auditory standards in corporate financial reporting in Nigeria: Emphasis on Compliance. *The Nigeria Accountant* 39 (4), 45-53.
- Oluwagbemiga, E. O. (2014). The use of voluntary disclosure in determining the quality of financial statements: Evidence from the Nigeria listed companies. *Serbian Journal of management*, 9(2), 263-280.
- Peecher, M. E., & Piercey, M. D. (2008). Judging audit quality in light of adverse outcomes: Evidence of outcome bias and reverse outcome bias. *Contemporary accounting research*, 25(1), 243-274
- Robinson, D. R., & Owens-Jackson, L. (2009). Audit committee characteristics and auditor changes. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 13. 117-133.
- Said, R. H., Zainuddin, Y., & Haron, H. (2009). The relationship between corporate social responsibility disclosure and corporate governance characteristics in Malaysian public listed companies. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 5(2), 212-226.
- Salaudeen, Y. M., Ibikunle, J., & Chima, E. I. (2015). Unethical accounting practice and financial reporting quality: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance, and Management Sciences*, 5(2), 143-150.